

ZettaLith: WSSCB manufacturing process

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1 Abstract

This paper details the manufacturing process of a Wafer-Scale Silicon Circuit Board (WSSCB), as used in ZettaLith.

1.1 WSSCB cross section

Figure 4a shows a cross section of a small portion of a WSSCB attached to a TRIMERA stack.

The WSSCB cross section shows an almost full thickness 300 mm silicon wafer of approximately 710 μm thick silicon. The WSSCB wafer contains integrated decoupling capacitors and power/ground TSVs. High speed signals between HBM4 stacks (not shown) and TRIMERA stacks, and between adjacent TRIMERA stacks attached to the WSSCB travel in the ultra-short range (USR) RDL signal wires.

The WSSCB contains silicon springs etched through the wafer at the spring gaps. These silicon springs may be FA spiral silicon springs, V beam silicon springs, folded beam silicon springs, or any other configuration of silicon spring appropriate to the design. An RDL-silicon indent prevents stress concentrators formed from overhang of the RDL layer into the spring gap, which could potentially cause delamination or crack propagation.

An elastomeric underfill prevents ingress of the liquid coolant into the WSSCB and its attached chips, without interfering with the elastic deformation of the silicon springs. The underfill is not required for thermal or mechanical reasons and is just a precaution against contaminants. It should be eliminated if the manufacturing process and 2-PIC coolant are sufficiently clean.

TRIMERA stack is connected to the WSSCB through microbump copper pillars joined by solder to microbump landing pads of the redistribution layer (RDL), which also contains signal wires and edge seals.

The WSSCB has UBM pads for connecting the CGA pillars of the PSU PCBs, the 800 GbE PCBs, and the PCIe 6.0 PCBs

Figure 4: WSSCB cross section

2 WSSCB Manufacturing Process

The manufacturing process for an WSSCB with stress relief builds upon mature CMOS wafer fabrication and silicon interposer manufacturing processes. The process detail given here will be largely redundant for foundries accustomed to producing silicon interposers, (TSMC, Intel, Samsung, and others), but may be useful as a starting process for other entrants to the field.

2.1 Starting Wafer

The process begins with selection of an n-type 300 mm silicon wafer having (100) crystal orientation as shown in Figure 4b. The wafer resistivity is chosen to be in the range of 1–10 Ω -cm, which provides a suitable substrate for the subsequent formation of deep trench capacitors while maintaining good mechanical properties for the WSSCB structure. The wafer is the standard 775 μ m thick, but the process flow can readily be adapted for other wafer thicknesses.

2.2 Integrated Decoupling Capacitor Formation

The initial etching process starts with deposition of a plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) oxide hardmask approximately 500 nm thick. The hardmask can be SiO_2 for simplicity, or Al_2O_3 for extreme selectivity (Drost et al, 2022). After photolithography using positive resist to define the capacitor regions, a dry etch process utilizing CF_4/O_2 chemistry creates recessed regions approximately 1 μ m deep. These recessed regions are sized larger than the eventual capacitor array to accommodate subsequent contact formation.

A second resist is applied. Within each recessed region photolithography defines the capacitors within each recessed region. An array of deep holes are formed with deep reactive ion etching (DRIE) using the Bosch process, alternating between SF_6 etch and C_4F_8 passivation steps, which creates high aspect ratio holes with nearly vertical sidewalls. The process temperature is maintained between -20°C and 20°C to ensure proper sidewall passivation and etching characteristics.

A critical doping step follows, where BBr_3 gas is used as a diffusion source at temperatures between 1000 – 1100°C for around 5 minutes. This high-temperature process ensures uniform p++ doping of all exposed silicon surfaces, including the sidewalls of the deep holes. This heavily doped region forms the outer negative plate of the capacitor structure, while forming a reverse biased diode with the n-wafer substrate.

The first dielectric layer is formed through dry thermal oxidation at 900 – 950°C in an O_2 atmosphere. This carefully controlled oxidation produces a high-quality thermal oxide layer 5-10 nm thick, with minimal defects and pinholes. The thermal oxide serves as the primary capacitor dielectric. This is performed after BBr_3 doping, but before the first polysilicon layer.

The first polysilicon layer is deposited using low-pressure chemical vapor deposition (LPCVD) at 580 – 620°C using silane (SiH_4) gas. This conformal deposition creates a polysilicon layer 100–200 nm thick on the sidewalls of the holes, forming the positive plate of the capacitor.

A second thermal oxidation step, performed under the same conditions as the first oxidation, creates another high-quality dielectric layer on the first polysilicon layer. The BBr_3 doped silicon is not further oxidized, as it is covered by the first polysilicon layer. This second oxide layer provides additional capacitance to the inner plate, nearly doubling the capacitance with no extra lithography steps.

The holes are then filled with a second LPCVD polysilicon deposition, performed at 580 – 620°C with in-situ phosphorus doping. This layer is deposited conformal plus overfill. While complete void-free filling is desired, small voids in the center of the filled holes are acceptable as they do not significantly impact the capacitor

Figure 4b: starting silicon 300 mm wafer

performance.

The wafer surface is then planarized using chemical-mechanical planarization (CMP), with the original oxide hard mask serving as a polish stop layer. A thorough post-CMP clean removes any residual slurry particles and contaminants.

Figure 4c shows an WSSCB cross section after formation of the integrated deep trench capacitor (DTC) decoupling capacitors in the wafer silicon. In practice, all areas of the wafer not used by other structures would be filled with decoupling capacitors to obtain maximum capacitance with minimum parasitic inductance.

The formation of DTCs for power supply decoupling is a prior art process, available at TSMC (Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company, the world's largest semiconductor foundry) under the trademark iCAP. The process flow described above is an estimate of TSMC's process flow and may not exactly match the actual process TSMC uses for iCAP.

The process for WSSCB decoupling capacitors varies from the TSMC iCAP process in that the capacitors may be nearly as deep as the full wafer thickness, which is typically 775 μm . This compares to less than 100 μm for iCAP DTCs in TSMC's trademarked chip-on-wafer-on-substrate (CoWoS-S) process, as CoWoS-S interposers are thinned to 100 μm , and wafer thinning must not reach the bottom of the blind holes etched for the capacitors. The extra potential depth of the decoupling capacitors can result in approximately 8 times the potential capacitance of iCAP DTC. However, in practice this extra capacitance is difficult to achieve, as the aspect ratio of the blind DTC holes would also need to be 8 times higher. Unless the aspect ratio can increase, the hole spacing at the surface of the wafer would need to increase, reducing the capacitance by the square of the increase in hole spacing. The ability to effectively use the extra available silicon depth to increase the capacitance of the decoupling capacitors requires extensive design of experiments (DoE) for optimization, which is beyond the scope of this process description.

2.3 TSV Formation

The through-silicon via (TSV) process requires precise control of etch depth to expose the copper-filled TSVs while maintaining wafer integrity. The starting substrate is a 300 mm silicon wafer with total thickness variation (TTV) of $\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$, providing a thickness range of 770–780 μm . The TSVs themselves are etched and filled at this stage, with the critical etch depth controlled to maintain a minimum 25 μm margin from the wafer surface in the thinnest possible wafer (770 μm), resulting in a maximum TSV depth of 745 μm .

The first step is ALD of an Al_2O_3 hardmask. The ALD process is conducted at 300°C using trimethylaluminum (TMA) and water vapor as precursors, with a pulse/purge sequence of 0.1s/4s. The self-limiting nature of ALD provides precise thickness control through cycle counting, with each cycle depositing approximately 1.1 \AA of Al_2O_3 . A total of 910 cycles (62 minutes) produces the target thickness of 100 nm, which provides excellent etch resistance for the subsequent deep silicon etch. The Al_2O_3 hardmask can achieve extremely high selectivity due to the formation of a non-volatile AlF_x layer during the Bosch process, with etch rates as low as 0.01 nm/min when using optimized passivation step timing (Drost et al, 2022).

Photolithography begins with hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) vapor prime at 150°C, followed by application of positive photoresist to a thickness of 1.2 μm via spin coating at 3000 rpm for 30 seconds. The resist undergoes a soft bake at 110°C for 60 seconds. The resist is then exposed using a photomask defining the TSV pattern of 50 μm diameter holes, with an exposure dose of 150 mJ/cm^2 . Post-exposure bake at 110°C for 60 seconds is followed by development in tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH)-based developer for 45 seconds and deionized water rinse.

The hardmask is then etched using BCl_3/Cl_2 plasma in a 3:1 ratio, with 600 W ICP

Figure 4c: form deep trench capacitor (DTC)

power and 100 W bias power at 5 mTorr pressure and 60°C. The etch process requires approximately 15 seconds, with endpoint detection via optical emission spectroscopy and a 10% overetch to ensure complete clearing of the Al₂O₃. The remaining photoresist is stripped using O₂ plasma at 800 W and 200°C for 3 minutes, followed by appropriate wet cleaning steps.

DRIE using the Bosch process creates the TSV holes. The process alternates between SF₆ etch steps (600 W source, 100 W bias) and C₄F₈ passivation steps (600 W source, 0 W bias), with cycle times of 5 and 3 seconds respectively. Chamber pressure is maintained at 20 mTorr, with substrate temperature controlled between -20°C and 20°C, achieving an etch rate of 5–10 μm per minute. Process variation is controlled through several factors: loading effects contribute approximately 1% variation (±7.7 μm), ARDE effects result in up to 2% variation (±15.4 μm), temperature-induced variation is controlled to less than 0.5% (±3.9 μm), and chamber symmetry effects contribute approximately 1% (±7.7 μm).

Following the deep etch, thorough cleaning removes fluorocarbon polymers using O₂ plasma at 1000 W for 10 minutes, followed by wet cleaning steps including hot piranha clean, deionized water rinse, dilute HF dip, and final rinse. The Al₂O₃ hardmask is then removed using 2.38% TMAH at room temperature for 2 minutes, followed by deionized water rinse and spin dry. This room-temperature TMAH process provides controlled removal of the hardmask using standard fab equipment and chemicals.

An example DRIE etched hole for power or ground TSV is shown. Due to the vastly different scales of features in the entire WSSCB assembly, only one TSV is shown. If the TSVs are 50 μm in diameter, and 100 μm pitch, a 300 mm wafer can fit approximately 7 million TSVs. A wafer-scale WSSCB may have several million TSVs in practice.

A thermal oxide (SiO₂) is then grown at 950–1000°C to a thickness of 1-2 μm, providing the primary dielectric isolation layer for the TSVs.

A stress-relief polymer layer, for example benzocyclobutene (BCB), is applied using spray coating equipment specialized for deep hole coverage. Multiple thin coats are applied with intermediate vacuum processing steps, followed by a final cure at 250°C, achieving a target thickness of 2–3 μm.

The conductive barrier and seed layers are deposited in two steps. First, a titanium nitride (TiN) barrier layer is deposited using metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) at 350–400°C to a thickness of 50–100 nanometers, providing excellent conformality. This is followed by Cu seed layer deposition using enhanced-ionization PVD with RF bias for directional deposition, achieving a thickness of 200–300 nanometers.

Copper electroplating fills the TSVs using a three-component additive system using suppressor (polyethylene glycol-based), accelerator (sulfopropyl-based), and leveler compounds. The current density is ramped from an initial 0.5 ASD through main fill at 1.5–2 ASD, concluding at 1 ASD. The plating bath is maintained at 22–24°C throughout the process.

Post-plating cleaning uses deionized water rinse and dilute H₂SO₄ clean. The wafer then undergoes a two-step chemical-mechanical planarization process, beginning with bulk copper removal at high pressure and speed, followed by final polish at reduced pressure and speed. Optical endpoint detection ensures proper planarization to the original wafer surface.

Final cleaning steps include brush scrub cleaning, deionized water rinse, surface inspection, and ionic contamination testing.

Figure 4d shows the WSSCB cross section at this processing stage. The power/ground or slow signal TSV is surrounded by the TSV dielectric and stress relief linings.

Figure 4d: etch and fill power TSVs

2.4 Formation of the RDL

The redistribution layer (RDL) formation process begins with the first-level interconnect layer connecting to the TSVs and decoupling capacitor structures. A silicon dioxide dielectric layer is deposited using PECVD at 350–400°C to achieve a thickness of $2.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. The deposition parameters maintain tensile stress below 100 MPa in the deposited film.

The first-level metallization employs a dual-damascene process creating both the contact via arrays and the redistribution traces in a single metal fill operation. Contact openings are patterned as arrays of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ diameter vias. For TSV contacts, there are many vias covering the TSV top surface. There may be as many as 1,800 vias, assuming $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ vias at a $1 \mu\text{m}$ pitch, on top of a $50 \mu\text{m}$ TSV. However, there will typically be many fewer, to allow for signal routing above the TSV, between power connection via and metal layer stacks. For decoupling capacitor polysilicon contacts, redundant vias are implemented. The via arrays provide redundancy in the contact structures while maintaining compatibility with subsequent RDL design rules.

Ar sputter cleaning is performed at 200–300 W RF bias power for 60 seconds. The WSSCB wafer is immediately transferred to the PVD chamber under N_2 purge to prevent native oxide formation.

The barrier and seed layers are then deposited. TSV and polysilicon decoupling contacts receive a stack of 30 nm Ti, 30 nm TiN, and 150 nm Cu seed layer.

Copper electroplating employs a bottom-up fill process with current density ramping from 0.5 to 1.5 ASD, conducted at $22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The plating continues until achieving $2 \mu\text{m}$ of overburden above the field areas. Post-plating anneal is performed at 150°C for 30 minutes in N_2 atmosphere, using a controlled ramp rate of $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$.

The copper overburden is removed using a two-step CMP process, using initial bulk removal followed by fine polishing, with optical endpoint detection ensuring proper planarization.

Perform inspection and repair using an automated FIB circuit edit machine. Bridging short circuits can be repaired by ion beam sputtering. Open circuits can be repaired by using a focused beam of ions (typically Ga) to deposit conductive material (typically Pt or W)

Five subsequent redistribution layers are formed using a consistent process flow. For each layer deposit 2–4 μm of low-k dielectric, such as SiCOH using PECVD.

This is followed by a standard copper dual damascene process with a minimum line width and spacing of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ at $1 \mu\text{m}$ pitch. This involves mask layers for vias and lines, both of which are stitched over the wafer, as the WSSCB is larger than the mask reticle.

These RDL layers are specifically designed to provide the high-density routing required for HBM4 and UCIe 2.0 connections, or subsequent versions of HBM and UCIe. The design incorporates redundant signal routing paths to enhance both manufacturing yield and operational fault tolerance.

Irrespective of the fault tolerance, each layer is automatically inspected and repaired using FIB circuit edit. Wafer scale WSSCBs are critical components of very high value systems and would likely have zero yield without extensive fault tolerance and intensive inspection and repair.

2.5 Power distribution

Power distribution is accomplished through vertical stacks of metal aligned with power-designated TSVs, connected by dense arrays of copper-filled vias between adjacent metal layers. This approach provides low-resistance power delivery while maintaining redundancy through multiple parallel paths.

The final layer includes landing pad formation for microbump attachment. A $10 \mu\text{m}$

thick dielectric layer is deposited, and $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ pad regions are opened. The pad metallization consists of $3.0 \mu\text{m}$ Ni-P, $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ Pd, and $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ Au, maintaining surface roughness below $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ RMS.

Figure 4e shows the WSSCB cross section at this processing stage. The RDL is formed on the top surface of silicon. The RDL contains multiple layers of signal lines. Almost all the signal lines are shown end-on, as lines going into the page rather than across it. Here six layers of signal lines, at $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ line width at $1 \mu\text{m}$ pitch are shown, though the number of layers may vary depending on the application. A signal microbump landing pad is shown, connected to signal lines. A power or ground microbump landing pad is shown on top of a stack of metal layers and arrays of vias connecting to the TSV. An edge seal is shown on each side of the SCB edge region and the spring gap regions of the RDL. The wafer is still at the full wafer thickness.

If the wafer is to be an entire WSSCB, it is not singulated into individual SCBs, so there are no SCB edges in the mask set.

2.6 Etch of the RDL Stack for the SCB edges and Spring Gaps

The RDL stack etch process begins with the deposition of a TiN hardmask on the completed RDL stack. The TiN is deposited using PECVD at $350\text{--}400^\circ\text{C}$ to achieve a thickness of 250 nm . The deposition uses N_2/TiCl_4 chemistry at $1\text{--}2$ Torr chamber pressure, achieving a deposition rate of approximately 2 nm/second .

Photolithography begins with HMDS vapor prime at 150°C . An ArF photoresist is applied at 3000 rpm to achieve 200 nm thickness, followed by a soft bake at 110°C for 60 seconds. The resist is exposed using an ArF scanner (193 nm) at 30 mJ/cm^2 . After a post-exposure bake at 110°C for 60 seconds, the resist is developed in standard ArF TMAH developer for 30 seconds, followed by deionized water rinse and spin dry at 2000 rpm for 30 seconds.

The hardmask pattern is transferred using a Cl_2/BCl_3 plasma etch in equal ratio, with 400 W source power and 100 W bias power. The chamber pressure is maintained at 5 mTorr with 60 sccm total flow rate and platen temperature at 60°C . The etch requires approximately 60 seconds with endpoint detection on the underlying oxide. The remaining photoresist is stripped using O_2 plasma at 800 W and 300 mTorr pressure, with 1000 sccm O_2 flow at 250°C for 2 minutes.

The main dielectric stack etch employs a single high-aspect-ratio anisotropic etch using $\text{CF}_4/\text{CHF}_3/\text{Ar}$ plasma in a $45:45:10$ ratio. The etch uses 2000 W source power and 200 W bias power at 10 mTorr pressure with 120 sccm total flow rate. The platen temperature is maintained at 15°C . At an expected etch rate of approximately 400 nm/minute , an initial timed etch of 54 minutes removes 90% of the target depth.

Endpoint detection employs multiple methods. Primary monitoring uses in-situ interferometry through endpoint windows incorporated in the empty corners of the WSSCB array. This is supplemented by RF bias voltage monitoring for silicon interface detection and periodic depth measurements using automated profilometry on the corner sites. After endpoint confirmation, a 10% timed overetch ensures complete clearing to the silicon surface. Total process time is around 65 minutes.

The hardmask is removed using SC1 clean ($\text{NH}_4\text{OH}:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in $1:1:5$ ratio) at 65°C for 10 minutes, followed by deionized water rinse for 5 minutes and spin dry at 2000 rpm for 30 seconds.

Quality control includes optical microscope inspection of spring gaps and edges, profilometer measurement of etch depth in corner regions, scanning electron microscope (SEM) inspection of sidewall profile, and surface roughness measurement of exposed silicon.

The result of this process is shown in Figure 4f, where the RDL 328 has been completely removed in the SCB edge region and the spring gap regions, exposing the underlying silicon.

Figure 4e: form redistribution layers (RDL)

Figure 4f: etch spring gaps in RDL

2.7 Inversion and Attachment to a Handle Wafer

This process begins with preparation of a prime grade 300 mm silicon handle wafer of standard 775 μm thickness, chosen for compatibility with automated wafer handling equipment. The handle wafer undergoes a thorough cleaning using a sulfuric peroxide mixture ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 4:1$) at 120°C for 10 minutes, followed by deionized water rinse and spin dry. A dehydration bake at 200°C for 5 minutes ensures complete removal of moisture.

A thermal release adhesive is applied to the handle wafer using spin coating. The adhesive is dispensed at 500 rpm for 5 seconds, then spread at 1500 rpm for 30 seconds to achieve a target thickness of 20 μm . Edge bead removal is performed using edge solvent dispense to ensure uniform adhesive thickness across the wafer. The adhesive undergoes a soft bake at 110°C for 2 minutes to remove solvents and stabilize the film.

The WSSCB wafer surface is prepared using a mild O_2 plasma ash at 200 W for 30 seconds, carefully controlled to avoid damage to the exposed metal pads. This is followed by a dehydration bake at 200°C for 5 minutes to ensure optimal bonding conditions.

The bonding process employs a specialized wafer bonding system with dual bond chucks. The handle wafer is loaded on the bottom chuck with the adhesive side up, while the WSSCB wafer is loaded on the top chuck facing downward. The wafers are aligned using an infrared alignment system with center alignment tolerance of $\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$ and angular alignment tolerance of $\pm 0.01^\circ$.

Initial contact between the wafers is made at the center under vacuum conditions. A uniform pressure of 0.3 MPa is applied across the wafer pair, and the temperature is ramped to 180°C at 20°C/minute. The temperature and pressure are maintained for 3 minutes to ensure complete adhesive bonding. The bonded pair is then cooled to 40°C while maintaining pressure, after which the vacuum is released and the bonded pair is separated from the bond chucks.

Quality control measures include acoustic microscopy inspection for void detection, infrared inspection for alignment verification, and edge inspection for adhesive overflow. The total thickness variation is measured, and bond strength is verified using calibrated pull tests on dummy samples processed under identical conditions.

Figure 4g shows the WSSCB cross section after inversion and attachment to the handle wafer using the thermal release adhesive. The RDL and landing pad structures are now facing downward against the adhesive layer, while the backside of the silicon substrate of the WSSCB is exposed for subsequent processing steps.

2.8 Exposure of the TSVs

The TSV exposure process begins with plasma etching of the silicon substrate to expose the copper-filled TSV structures. Backgrinding is intentionally omitted to eliminate mechanical stress on the wafer. The plasma etch employs SF_6/O_2 chemistry in an 80:20 ratio with 2000 W source power and 30 W bias power, the latter kept intentionally low to minimize surface damage. Chamber pressure is maintained at 20 mTorr with 100 sccm total flow rate, while platen temperature is regulated at 15°C.

The etch targets a removal depth of 30 μm , to a level slightly beyond the TSV tips, with an expected etch rate of 2 $\mu\text{m}/\text{minute}$. Endpoint detection employs both optical emission spectroscopy for copper signal detection and RF bias voltage monitoring, with the regular array of TSVs providing a strong endpoint signal. The total etch time is approximately 15 minutes, including a brief overetch to ensure complete copper exposure.

The result of this process is shown in Figure 4h, depicting WSSCB cross section with slightly protruding TSV.

Figure 4g: invert and attach to handle wafer

Figure 4h: etch silicon of back of wafer

2.9 CMP of back-side of wafer

Following the plasma etch, chemical mechanical planarization (CMP) employs a non-selective silica-based slurry with 2 psi down force. Platen and carrier speeds are set to 60 and 57 rpm respectively, with slurry flow maintained at 200 mL/minute. The CMP process continues for 35 μm (approximately 30 seconds) to achieve less than 50 nm step height between copper and silicon surfaces. Post-CMP cleaning utilizes PVA brush scrub followed by deionized water rinse and spin dry.

Quality control measurements include surface profilometry for co-planarity verification, optical microscopy for TSV exposure confirmation, AFM measurement of surface roughness, four-point probe testing for TSV electrical continuity, and cross-section SEM analysis of test structures.

The result of this process is shown in Figure 4i, depicting the WSSCB cross section with an exposed and planarized TSV with minimal topography between copper and silicon surfaces. The final WSSCB thickness remains approximately 710 μm , providing robust mechanical stability for subsequent handling steps.

The 710 μm thickness is not important - if previous processing variations allow, the CMP depth may be reduced, leaving the final WSSCB thickness greater than 710 μm .

Figure 4i: planarize back of wafer using CMP

2.10 Dielectric layer deposition and etch

A PECVD process deposits a silicon oxynitride (SiON) dielectric layer. The thickness of this layer is around 2 μm , optimized for dielectric isolation of the TSV connections. The deposition occurs at 350°C with a base deposition rate of 80 nm/minute, using SiH_4 , N_2O , and NH_3 as precursor gases. Chamber pressure is maintained at 3 Torr with 500 W RF power. While stress control through $\text{NH}_3/\text{N}_2\text{O}$ ratio adjustment remains important for film integrity, the >700 μm silicon substrate thickness means this layer does not significantly influence wafer bow from RDL stress on the opposite side.

Photolithographic patterning of the dielectric layer begins with HMDS vapor prime, followed by application of thick positive photoresist. The resist thickness is 3 μm , with spin speed adjusted accordingly. The resist undergoes soft bake at 110°C for 90 seconds. Exposure dose is 300 mJ/cm^2 , followed by post-exposure bake at 110°C for 90 seconds. Development uses TMAH-based chemistry for 90 seconds.

The dielectric etch employs $\text{CF}_4/\text{O}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ chemistry at 50 mTorr pressure, with 800 W ICP power and 200 W bias power. O_2 flow is adjusted to control sidewall profile. The etch rate approximates 200 nm/minute, with endpoint detection via optical emission spectroscopy and 10% overetch. Resist removal uses O_2 plasma at 800 W and 200°C, followed by wet cleaning.

2.11 UBM formation

Under-bump metallization (UBM) begins with in-situ sputter clean using Ar plasma at 300 W for 60 seconds at 5 mTorr. The UBM stack is deposited sequentially without breaking vacuum, using Ti adhesion layer (50 nm, 1000 W DC power, 3 mTorr), Ni barrier layer (500 nm, 1500 W DC power, 3 mTorr), and Au finish layer (100 nm, 1000 W DC power, 3 mTorr).

UBM patterning employs 4 μm thick positive photoresist, processed with soft bake at 110°C for 90 seconds, exposure at 250 mJ/cm^2 , post-exposure bake at 110°C for 90 seconds, and TMAH-based development for 90 seconds. Ion beam etching at 500 V beam voltage and 300 mA beam current, with 75° angle and stage rotation, removes the metal stack. Etch times are approximately 2 minutes for Au, 8 minutes for Ni, and 1 minute for Ti, with endpoint detection for each layer.

Post-etch cleaning uses O_2 plasma ash followed by wet clean sequence of acetone rinse, IPA rinse, and deionized water rinse. Final clean uses mild O_2 plasma followed by deionized water rinse and N_2 dry.

Quality control measurements include film stress at multiple process steps, physical

measurements via profilometry, X-ray fluorescence, and scanning electron microscopy of test structures, and electrical testing for dielectric breakdown, TSV-to-UBM continuity, and isolation resistance.

The result of this process is shown in Figure 4j, depicting the WSSCB cross section with UBM. The final WSSCB thickness remains approximately 710 μm .

2.12 Hardmask and Passivation Etch for Spring Gaps and Edges

The process for forming the spring gaps and SCB edges proceeds through selective etching utilizing a hardmask. The hardmask provides etch resistance for both the dielectric removal and subsequent deep silicon etching, while design considerations ensure robust interface formation between layers.

The process begins with ALD of an Al_2O_3 hardmask layer. The ALD process is conducted at 300°C using TMA and H_2O vapor as precursors, with a pulse/purge sequence of 0.1s/4s. The self-limiting nature of ALD provides precise thickness control through cycle counting, with each cycle depositing approximately 1.1 Å of Al_2O_3 . A total of 910 cycles (62 minutes) produces the target thickness of 100 nm, which provides sufficient etch resistance for both the dielectric etch and subsequent deep silicon etch, given the extremely high selectivity of Al_2O_3 to the Bosch process [1].

A TiN hardmask is deposited on the on the Al_2O_3 hardmask to protect the Al_2O_3 during back-side dielectric etch. The TiN is deposited using PECVD at 350–400°C to achieve a thickness of 100 nm. The deposition uses N_2/TiCl_4 chemistry at 1–2 Torr chamber pressure, achieving a deposition rate of approximately 2 nm/second. Photolithography begins with HMDS vapor prime at 150°C, followed by application of positive photoresist to a thickness of 1.2 μm via spin coating at 3000 rpm for 30 seconds. The resist undergoes a soft bake at 110°C for 60 seconds. The resist is then exposed using a photomask defining the spring gaps and SCB edges, with an exposure dose of 150 mJ/cm^2 . The TiN hardmask is used to pattern the etch of the Al_2O_3 hardmask and the back-side dielectric.

Post-exposure bake occurs at 110°C for 60 seconds, followed by development in TMAH-based developer for 45 seconds and deionized water rinse.

The hardmask stack is patterned using a Cl_2/BCl_3 plasma etch in equal ratio, with 600 W ICP source power and 100 W bias power. The chamber pressure is maintained at 5 mTorr with 60 sccm total flow rate and platen temperature at 60°C. The etch requires approximately 40 seconds with endpoint detection on the underlying oxide via optical emission spectroscopy, and a 10% overetch to ensure complete clearing of the Al_2O_3 .

With the photoresist still in place, the 2 μm SiON dielectric layer is etched using $\text{CF}_4/\text{O}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ chemistry at 50 mTorr pressure, with 800 W ICP power and 200 W bias power. The O_2 flow is adjusted to achieve vertical sidewalls. The etch rate approximates 200 nm/minute, resulting in a total etch time of approximately 10 minutes. Endpoint detection via optical emission spectroscopy ensures complete removal of the dielectric layer, with a 10% overetch.

Following the dielectric etch, the photoresist is stripped using O_2 plasma at 800 W and 200°C for 3 minutes, followed by appropriate wet cleaning steps. The removal of photoresist at this stage, rather than retaining it for subsequent processing, reduces organic contamination in the DRIE chamber used for the following process steps. This cleaning choice is enabled by the excellent selectivity of the Al_2O_3 hardmask, which alone is sufficient for the subsequent deep silicon etch.

The process includes inspection steps following the dielectric etch to verify pattern transfer and critical dimensions. Alignment of the pattern to the opposite side of the wafer is verified within standard backside alignment tolerances, with the RDL design rules accommodating normal alignment variations. This approach ensures reliable spring formation without requiring exceptionally tight alignment control.

Figure 4j: deposit and etch dielectric and UBM

Figure 4k shows the WSSCB cross section after these process steps. The hard mask is shown with exaggerated thickness around 20 times the actual thickness. A 100 nm hardmask layer would not be visible on the scale of this cross section.

2.13 RDL-silicon indent

The pattern dimensions in this back-side mask are designed so that the spring gap and edge patterns are wider in the RDL etch than the final width at the bottom of the back-side of the deep silicon trench, accounting for maximum expected alignment variation and DRIE process variation.

This results in an RDL-silicon indent of approximately 10 μm . The exact amount is not critical, as long as there is no overhang of the RDL layers over the silicon.

The larger the RDL-silicon indent is, the less room there is for signal lines in the RDL layers of springs. Since large numbers of signal lines for HBM4 signals and UCIe 2.0 signals cross the springs, the RDL-silicon indent should not be excessively wide.

This design approach eliminates potential stress concentrators that could occur from RDL overhang into the spring gaps.

2.14 Spring Gap and SCB Edge Etch

The spring gap and SCB edge formation process utilizes DRIE to create high-aspect-ratio trenches through the silicon substrate. The process benefits from trench geometry, where features exceed 100 μm in length, enabling aspect ratios of 100:1 or greater. This geometric advantage, compared to circular hole features, allows for more efficient material transport and enhanced etch performance. Minimum trench widths are maintained at around 8 μm to achieve controlled high-aspect-ratio etching.

The DRIE process employs a modified Bosch process optimized for deep trench etching. The chamber is maintained at -20°C with backside helium cooling at 10 Torr pressure. The process alternates between etch and passivation cycles at 15 mTorr chamber pressure, optimized for deep trench penetration. During the etch cycle, SF_6 plasma is generated using 800 W source power and 120 W bias power for a duration of 6 seconds. The subsequent passivation cycle utilizes C_4F_8 chemistry with 600 W source power and no bias power for 2.5 seconds, with the reduced passivation time reflecting the enhanced transport characteristics of trench geometry.

The etch proceeds at 8–12 μm per minute, significantly faster than comparable hole etching processes, resulting in a total process time of 70–90 minutes. In-situ monitoring employs laser interferometry for depth tracking, while optical emission spectroscopy provides primary endpoint detection. The endpoint detection system monitors silicon etch products and detects interaction with the underlying thermal release adhesive layer, providing a clear signal of etch completion. Secondary endpoint verification utilizes laser interferometry signal changes, chamber pressure variations, and RF bias voltage shifts.

Process control focuses on maintaining vertical or slightly positive sidewall profiles, which can affect spring mechanical characteristics, and must meet the RDL etches to ensure there is no overhang of the RDL layer. The ion angular distribution is monitored and controlled through process parameters to achieve the desired profile. Particular attention is paid to minimizing sidewall scalloping, especially on spring surfaces where mechanical properties are relevant.

Upon initial endpoint detection, the etch continues for an additional 20 seconds to ensure complete pattern transfer through local variations in etch rate. The process concludes with a chamber clean cycle to remove adhesive interaction products and maintain process stability.

Quality control measurements include scanning electron microscopy inspection of spring profiles, trench width measurements, verification of RDL-silicon indent

Figure 4k: deposit Al_2O_3 hardmask, pattern and etch spring gaps in back-side dielectric layer

maintenance, sidewall angle measurement, and scallop size quantification. Particular attention is paid to detecting any micro-masking effects that could impact spring mechanical properties. The mechanical integrity of formed springs undergoes verification through appropriate test structures, which may be placed in the otherwise empty processor array corners.

The resulting structures exhibit clean, vertical profiles with controlled dimensions, enabling reliable spring operation and precise SCB edge definition. The process achieves complete wafer penetration while maintaining critical feature dimensions and avoiding RDL interaction.

Figure 4l shows the WSSCB cross section after spring gap and SCB edge through-silicon etches. The RDL-silicon indent is shown.

2.15 Release from handle wafer, with no dicing step

The release process utilizes a temperature-controlled vacuum chuck with multi-zone heating capability to ensure uniform temperature distribution across the handle wafer. The chuck temperature increases at a controlled rate until reaching the adhesive release temperature of 150°C. The temperature maintains at this point for 60 seconds, with uniformity controlled to $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ across the wafer surface. Force sensors monitor the adhesive state transition, providing verification of proper release conditions.

Following removal from the handle wafer, the WSSCB undergoes a three-stage cleaning process to remove all adhesive residue. The initial stage employs a thermal adhesive removal solvent at 50°C for 5 minutes with 40 kHz ultrasonic agitation. This solvent may vary according to the specifications of the manufacturer of the thermal release adhesive. A secondary cleaning stage consists of sequential 2-minute rinses in isopropyl alcohol and deionized water, followed by nitrogen drying. The final cleaning stage utilizes an O_2/Ar plasma at 200 W power and 200 mTorr pressure for 2 minutes, ensuring complete removal of any organic residues.

Quality control measures include visual inspection for adhesive residue and potential spring damage, along with surface cleanliness verification. Metrology steps verify final thickness, measure any warpage, and confirm spring and spring gap dimensions remain within specification. The process maintains traceability for each WSSCB, recording release yield data and cleaning effectiveness for each wafer processed.

This release and cleaning sequence completes the fabrication process, producing individual WSSCBs ready for subsequent test and assembly operations. The process requires no additional dicing steps, for either a WSSCB, or a wafer with many individual SCBs. Any individual SCBs achieved full separation during the previous deep silicon etch process, simplifying handling and reducing the potential for damage to critical features. The use of through wafer silicon etch for singulation also allows irregular configurations of WSSCBs on a single wafer, which could not be singulated with a wafer saw. Singulating the wafer using the spring gap etch also results in less overall processing, cleaning, and yield loss.

Figure 4m shows a cross section of an SCB after release from the handle wafer. As the cross section has a SCB edge, it is from a wafer divided into multiple SCBs. A WSSCB has no etched SCB edges. Otherwise, the processing of a WSSCB and a wafer with many individual SCBs is essentially the same.

2.16 WSSCB Functional Test

Passive systems of interconnects create a problem for testing, as there can be no JTAG or BIST circuits. An WSSCB wafer will typically have on the order of 20 million ultra-short reach (USR) wires in its RDL layer, being mostly HBM4 signal connections and UCIe 2.0 connections. These ~20 million USR wires will have ~40 million end points, connected to microbump landing pads. Although the wires have fault tolerance, and WSSCB is optically inspected and repaired at each RDL layer,

Figure 4l: DRIE Bosch etch spring gaps and, if not a complete WSSCB, the SCB chip edges

Figure 4m: invert, detach from handle wafer

the WSSCB should still be thoroughly tested, as the value of chips attached to a single wafer scale WSSCB – up to around 172 HBM4 memory stacks, and 172 logic stacks – can be significant. However, existing ATE is poorly suited for testing wafer scale passive structures such as the WSSCB. There are several problems:

- The WSSCB cannot help with the testing of its ~20 million USR wires. With no JTAG or BIST, each wire must be tested individually for open or short circuits.
- The microbump landing pads are small and high density (large arrays of 28 μm pads at 73 μm pitch for HBM3 and HBM4), making conventional probes unsuitable.
- If there are only hundreds of probes on the test card, and a probe card lasts 1 million touchdowns, the probe card will wear out after only 10 wafers or so.
- A single probe card with only a few hundred probes would likely be impossible to design or would place massive constraints on the positions of wire end-points to be tested. The MEMS probe card described here places no constraints on the design of the WSSCB.
- The ATE equipment is massive ‘overkill’ for the application. The testing of a passive WSSCB does not need extremely fast ATE electronics with millions of test vectors.

2.17 Simple passive MEMS test probe chip

The WSSCB testing process employs a specialized micro electromechanical systems (MEMS) test probe chip to enable simultaneous testing of all signal connections within each SCB module position.

The MEMS test probe chip measures approximately 32 mm \times 19 mm and contains more than 112,000 individual probe springs, enabling simultaneous testing of all HBM and UCIe 2.0 signal lines of one SCB module of the WSSCB.

This includes approximately 6,000 HBM signal connections and 50,000 UCIe signal lines, each of which must be contacted at both ends to test them. There are also a small number of miscellaneous slow signals, and a large number of power and ground connections, so the total number of probe springs will be around 160,000.

Figure 4n shows a small section of the test spring mask of the simple MEMS test chip. Figure 4o shows the test probe springs at the instant they touch down on the landing pads in the RDL. Figure 4p shows the test probes under full compression.

The test probe springs have a spiral configuration to minimize scrub. Scrub magnitude is almost completely cancelled by the constantly rotating scrub direction along the length of spiral cantilever. Minimizing scrub is important to maintain probe chip lifetime.

2.18 Test springs completely unrelated to WSSCB silicon springs

It is important to note that the test probe springs are completely unrelated to the silicon springs that provide thermal and mechanical stress isolation within the WSSCB.

2.19 Testing TSVs

The majority of TSVs in an WSSCB are power and ground TSVs. However, the WSSCB design also includes a small number of signal TSVs that connect microbump landing pads on the top surface to connections on the bottom surface of the WSSCB for I3C two-wire connections to the PSU PCBs, and GbE and PCIe connections. To simplify testing of these connections without requiring probe access to the bottom surface of the WSSCB, each signal TSV incorporates a connection verification microbump landing pad on the top surface. This verification pad connects independently to the TSV through the RDL layers. Testing the connectivity between the signal microbump landing pad and its corresponding verification pad effectively tests the TSV connection without requiring bottom-side probing, maintaining the simplicity of the single-sided test approach.

2.20 Testing the edges of the array

The WSSCB employs a specialized routing strategy at the edges of the module

Figure 4n: MEMS test probe chip mask

Figure 4o: test probes touch-down

Figure 4p: test probes under compression

array, which are adjacent to 800 GbE and PCIE 6.0 sites instead of other SCB modules. This strategy enables testing with a single probe chip design. Instead of direct point-to-point connections between the BIDs UCIe interfaces and the 800 GbE or PCIE 6.0 TSVs, the connections follow a loop-back pattern. From the BID each UCIe signal routes to its corresponding 800 GbE or PCIE 6.0 TSV, then continues to a test microbump landing pad positioned where the next module's UCIe connection would be if it were an interior position. This design eliminates the need for multiple probe chip configurations for testing interior, corner, and edge array positions.

2.21 WSSCB test system

The test system mechanical architecture consists of a heavily reinforced precision Z-axis stage supporting the MEMS probe chip, with force feedback control to prevent probe damage. The stage must handle a total contact force of around 320 kilogram-force (kgf) due to the approximately 160,000 individual probes in the array, each operating at around 2 grams-force (gf). Lower contact forces, such as 0.5 gf, can reduce the total probe force to approximately 40 kgf. However, such low contact force requires specific attention to the probe design and may become unreliable after a smaller number of probe touchdowns. This substantial force necessitates highly robust mechanical design of both the Z-axis stage and the X-Y positioning stage. The stage maintains parallelism between the probe chip and WSSCB surface within ± 10 arc-seconds to ensure uniform contact across all probe points. A precision X-Y stage positions each module location under the probe chip with ± 2 μm accuracy, with sufficient stiffness to maintain position accuracy under the high contact forces.

The WSSCB is especially designed to withstand high contact forces in the presence of contaminants, as shown in Figure 2k, though contaminants of the size shown in Figure 2k should be avoided!

The probe chip connects to simple continuity testing circuitry that verifies the integrity of daisy-chained connections through the probe array. The test sequence proceeds as follows:

1. The WSSCB wafer is loaded onto the test chuck and aligned using standard wafer handling equipment.
2. The system moves to the first module position and performs a probe touchdown with controlled force ramping.
3. The continuity test executes in under 100 milliseconds, checking all signal paths simultaneously.
4. The system records a binary go/no-go result for the module position.
5. The probe lifts and the X-Y stage moves the wafer to the next module position.
6. Steps 2-5 repeat until all module positions are tested.

The entire wafer test completes in a few minutes, with 172 touchdowns for a typical wafer-scale WSSCB. The system generates a wafer map indicating the status of each module position, which drives subsequent automated assembly decisions.

For WSSCBs meeting minimum yield criteria, the map determines chip attachment strategy:

- "Go" positions receive known good die (KGD) HBM stacks and logic dies
 - "No-go" positions receive dummy mechanical HBM stacks and bypass-enabled logic dies
- The bypass-enabled logic dies maintain system connectivity by routing UCIe 2.0 signals between adjacent modules, effectively removing the failed module from the logical topology while preserving mechanical and thermal characteristics of the array.

Each probe chip typically achieves one million touchdowns before replacement, enabling testing of approximately 6,000 wafers per probe. This allows for scheduled maintenance and probe replacement during regular system maintenance intervals.

The simplicity of this test methodology, combined with high parallelism and rapid execution, enables comprehensive testing of the passive WSSCB structures without requiring BIST or JTAG capabilities. This approach achieves extensive coverage of critical signal paths while maintaining practical test times and costs.

The test results provide essential data for:

- Assembly optimization
- Yield analysis and process control
- System configuration management
- Reliability prediction

This testing strategy balances thoroughness with throughput, enabling practical implementation of wafer-scale integration while maintaining system reliability through comprehensive interconnect verification.

2.22 Chip Attach

The chip attachment process for the WSSCB follows established microbump attachment procedures while accommodating multiple chip types and configurations. The process utilizes conventional thermal compression bonding techniques for microbump connections.

HBM4 and logic stacks are attached to the "go" positions identified during WSSCB testing. All chips maintain identical orientation to ensure consistent thermal and mechanical characteristics across the array.

Any "no-go" positions identified during testing are populated with physical dummy HBM stacks and passive RDL dummy logic stack chips. These dummy components maintain the mechanical and thermal uniformity of the array while providing signal bypass functionality through the passive RDL connections.

If the extensive fault tolerance of the WSSCB leads to sufficient yield so that any WSSCB with "no go" positions can be discarded, then the dummy chip stacks are not required, and don't need to be developed.

The WSSCB architecture supports varied logic stack configurations within a single array while maintaining a standardized BID interface between the logic stacks and WSSCB.

The CPU modules in this configuration handle high-speed computations not suitable for the main array, as commonly required in CPU-GPU systems for AI inference.

This flexibility extends to future implementations, where arrays of chips on a single WSSCB design can become increasingly varied and application-specific as new compatible logic stacks are developed.

For commercial viability, the CPU SLD do not need to be leading edge. They only need to provide adequate compute power to load data to the main TRIMERA array, for transformer inference, and to provide associated computation that is not suitable for the main array.

The attachment process employs precision placement equipment with the following capabilities:

- Placement accuracy: $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$
- Angular alignment: $\pm 0.01^\circ$
- Temperature control: $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ across the attachment region
- Force control: $\pm 2\%$ of target force

This level of precision ensures reliable microbump connections while preventing damage to the underlying WSSCB structure or the chips being attached.

Quality control measures include:

- Real-time force and temperature monitoring
- Post-attachment X-ray inspection
- Electrical verification of attached components

Figure 4q: plasma clean and attach chip stacks

The chip attachment process maintains consistent quality across all array configurations while accommodating the flexibility inherent in the WSSCB architecture, enabling diverse system implementations using standardized manufacturing processes.

Figure 4q shows the WSSCB cross section after chip attach of chip stacks. The chips microbumps provide the solder for the microbumps, and the WSSCB has the landing pads. A cross section of a silicon spring with a spring gap on either side is shown. The RDL-silicon indents at the spring gap and SCB edges are shown.

2.23 Underfill may not be required

The purpose of the underfill is to keep contaminants out of the ZettaLith structure. It is not required (in fact, slightly counterproductive) for mechanical stability or heat conduction. If the coolant and operating environment of ZettaLith is sufficiently clean, an underfill should not be required.

2.24 Underfill (if required)

The WSSCB underfill process represents a significant departure from conventional underfill methods, both in materials and application technique. Traditional underfill processes employ high modulus epoxy polymers to distribute mechanical and thermal expansion stresses between chips and substrates. These materials and their application methods are unsuitable for the WSSCB for several reasons.

First, conventional high modulus underfills would interfere with the mechanical function of the silicon springs, which are designed to provide stress relief between chips and substrate. The springs function most effectively when not constrained by rigid materials.

Second, conventional underfill dispensing equipment, designed for individual chip attachment, becomes impractical for the WSSCB's array of closely-spaced chips. The standard process of dispensing underfill along chip edges and allowing capillary flow would require multiple transfers between chip attach and underfill equipment as each ring of chips is attached from the center outward. This would significantly increase handling of the high-value populated WSSCB and reduce manufacturing throughput.

Third, the complex geometry of the WSSCB, with its network of silicon springs and narrow gaps between chips, makes conventional edge dispensing unreliable, as it could lead to void formation and incomplete filling of the spring structures.

These challenges are addressed by a fundamentally different (and far simpler) approach: dipping the populated WSSCB into a bath of low modulus elastomeric underfill material. This simple solution eliminates the complexity of edge dispensing and ensures complete filling of all spaces within the WSSCB structure. The elastomer naturally wicks through the silicon spring gaps from the underside of the WSSCB, using these gaps as a network of channels to reach all areas requiring underfill.

2.25 Underfill material

For this new process, KE-1280-A/B silicone elastomer from Shin-Etsu was selected. This two-component addition cure material forms a true elastomer with Shore A hardness of 24, providing minimal mechanical interference with the silicon spring structure while maintaining position after cure. The material offers excellent electrical properties (volume resistivity 1.0 TΩ·m, dielectric strength 25 kV/mm) and is UL 94 V-0 rated. Despite its relatively high viscosity (1700 cP), calculations indicate it should wick through the structure in less than 1 second due to capillary action.

Key advantages of KE-1280-A/B include:

- Addition cure chemistry ensures complete cure in confined spaces with no byproducts

- Good adhesion to silicon and circuit board materials
- 6-hour working time decouples underfill process from elastomer mixing
- Heat cure at 120°C for 1 hour
- Operating temperature range of -40 to +180°C
- Self-leveling properties
- Controlled low molecular weight siloxane content

If an underfill elastomer is to be used, chemical compatibility with 2-PIC coolant needs to be established.

2.26 Underfill process

The underfill process consists of five simple steps:

1. First, the fully populated WSSCB is lowered into a bath of uncured elastomeric underfill material. The immersion depth must reach above the bottom surface of the WSSCB but remain below the top surface, a tolerance easily achieved given the approximately 700 μm difference between these levels.
2. Second, the low viscosity elastomer wicks through the silicon spring gaps from the underside of the WSSCB. The spring gaps provide a network of channels allowing the elastomer to flow into the microbump regions under all chips in the array and up through the narrow gaps between chips.
3. Third, excess uncured elastomer is wiped from the bottom surface of the WSSCB. The silicon springs, being substantially more robust than typical silicon interposer structures, require no special protection during this step.
4. Fourth, the elastomer undergoes thermal cure. Extended cure times or elevated temperatures may be employed to ensure complete cure throughout the structure, as there are no adverse effects from overcure.
5. Finally, the bottom surface of the WSSCB undergoes O_2 plasma cleaning to remove any residual elastomer that could interfere with subsequent CGA column attachment. A second plasma cleaning step may be required if optical inspection reveals remaining elastomer residue.

This simplified process eliminates the complexity of conventional underfill dispensing while ensuring complete and void-free underfill coverage throughout the WSSCB structure.

Figure 4r shows the WSSCB cross section after underfill. The underfill silicone elastomer wicks through the entire populated WSSCB via the spring gaps and into the microbump region under the chip stacks.

Figure 4r: optional underfill